

DIGITAL DIVIDE IS NOT A RURAL ISSUE: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS FROM THE STUDENTS' & LOCAL PEOPLE'S PERSPECTIVES IN AN INDIAN METROPOLITAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

With the emergence of digital society as a parallel entity to traditional culture, an individual's membership now encompasses both the physical and digital realms. Since 2000, and especially in 2015 and 2016, India as a developing country has made notable progress in this area. This resulted in a digital revolution in the traditional systems of economics, politics, culture, education, religion, and law, but this change has also brought to light an important issue: the digital divide. We could find several studies on urban and rural digital divides because the gap is significant in these two diasporas. But hardly any literature can be found that highlights the digital divide in another segment of metropolitan areas, which is 'under-resourced urban areas'. The study discloses the digital gap between these two segments of an Indian metropolitan city, Kolkata, such as affluent city areas and under-resourced urban areas, with the help of socio-cultural and socio-economic factors. A qualitative survey method was used with an unstructured questionnaire from 100 residents who are the students and others, both from the affluent and the under-resourced urban communities. The study reveals a visible digital gap in the livelihood and utilization of the people between these two segments of the metropolitan city. The outcome provides a path forward to develop more inclusive strategies to bridge the digital divide between various metropolitan segments.

Keywords: Digital Divide, Under-resourced Urban Areas, Affluent City Area, Socio-cultural Factors, Economic Factors, Developing Country

INTRODUCTION

The world is evolving in the digital age. Thus, much like any other societal feature and social relations, digital society, digital space, digital capital, digital relations, digital access, and so forth have become increasingly significant to sociology. The terms "information society" (Dijk, 2006) and "network society" (Castells, 2010) are used to characterize the digitalized world. The society that has arisen as a result of information and communication technology is referred to by these phrases. The digital revolution was sparked by a technical breakthrough that began in the 1970s in the United States under the information and communication technological paradigm. The political and economic landscape of Western and European societies was altered by this new paradigm. Owing to its promotion of individual creativity, freedom, and entrepreneurship, the new technological paradigm outperformed the electronics industry's early ascent in the 1940s–1960s (Castells, 2010, p. 4). According to Castells (2010, p. 5), social factors—like individual inventiveness and entrepreneurialism—play a significant role in the process of scientific discovery, technological

innovation, and social applications. As a result, society shapes technological change rather than technology determining it. The intricate network of interactions between technology and society, however, determines the outcomes. According to Castells (2010), technology is part of society and cannot be separated from it. Since the Internet and information and communication technology were introduced at the beginning of the twenty-first century, India has been a part of the digital society. But a true digital revolution did not begin to emerge until a pivotal moment in 2016 brought about by Reliance Communication Ltd.'s introduction of Reliance Jio Infocomm Ltd. In India, this revolution ushered in a new era of digitalization and paved the way for the later smartphone revolution (Laskar, 2023). One way to compare digital society to physical society is as a voluntary membership in both. Physical society is defined as the tangible presence of social structures and the outward manifestation of social ties. We acknowledge the importance of abstract concepts like standards, values, and conventions as fundamental components of society. Social, cultural, and legal regulations govern human behaviour and relationships in the physical world, whereas online conduct in the digital world is subject to loose legal regulations. These rules, however, are not comparable to the social control systems found in actual society (Laskar, 2023).

India has the world's largest population and is a developing economy. India was also impacted by the digitization boom. Therefore, it will be important to observe whether or not digitization spreads equally throughout society. All countries' urban Diasporas are generally thought to be digitally prosperous. But in a country like India, where there is a considerable economic difference among its citizens, does digital society serve a similar function to all, such as under-resourced urban areas and affluent community residence places, or not? In India, the population of under-resourced urban regions is growing, resulting in poor quality of life, restricted digital access, and inadequate digital life services. In 2022, about 100 million people live in under-resourced urban areas, surpassing Australia's total population (India Housing Report, 2022). Hence the digital divide must be present there. The concept of the "digital divide", "technology acceptance model" (TAM), "theory of cultural lag" have been proposed in this paper.

The difference that arises between individuals who have sufficient access to ICTs and those who have less access is known as the "digital divide," according to Centeio (2017). His research indicates that the first wave of the digital divide focussed on disparities in computer and Internet accessibility, while the second wave focussed on social and cultural issues, such as varying levels of knowledge (Das & Bhattacharyya, 2023). The third level of digital divide, outlined by van Deursen & Helsper (2015), focuses on the consequences or benefits of digital use. Individuals who overcome accessibility issues, learn digital skills, and participate in digital activities will eventually seek to attain positive online results or returns.

The users' behavioural purpose to utilize the digital tools is influenced by their attitudes and level of convenience with it. The way the system should be used is determined by the behavioural goal. The "Technology Acceptance Model" no longer takes the user's disposition into account (Das & Bhattacharyya, 2023).

According to Ogburn, "technological progress produces rapid changes in the material aspects of our culture, but the non-material aspects fail to adjust or they do so only after an excessive time lag. As a result, many troublesome social problems are created" (Brinkman & Brinkman, 1997).

The majority of the previous research focuses on the digital divide between urban and rural areas in western context mostly and few in Indian context. But less attention is being paid on issues of digital divide in the under-resourced urban area. Hence the study highlights the digital gap between the affluent city area and under-resourced urban area of metropolitan city like Kolkata which is the capital city of West Bengal, a state of India, and from the students' and other residential lens of those areas. Thus, the present study features the following research questions to bridge the digital gap in the previous literatures by comparing the both affluent and under-resourced urban areas of Indian metropolitan contexts, such as :

RQ-1. What factors of the society determine the digital divide?

RQ-2. What are the factors behind these two groupings of residents, affluent city areas and under-resourced residential areas with respect to the digital divide in Indian metropolises like Kolkata?

URBAN POVERTY AND DIGITAL DIVIDE

A substantial amount of research indicates that as urban poverty is growing and greater attention should be paid to it. Urbanization is the movement of more people from rural to urban locations in recent years. According to Mitlin (2004), almost half of the world's population resides in cities. In addition, the UNDP predicted that by 2050, over 66% of people would reside in cities. If more people migrate to metropolitan regions and lack education and skills, the amount of poverty in those places may rise. According to a UNDP study, city growth and urbanization will increase urban poverty, which will rise above the level of poverty in rural areas. For instance, Chinn & Fairlie's (2007) study on 160 nations showed compelling evidence that the primary cause of the digital divide is not only wealth inequality but also a lack of education. Furthermore, their analysis demonstrated that educational disparities account for the majority of the disparity between individuals with and without access to technology. According to Chinn & Fairlie (2007), educated people have a greater need for computers to support their daily activities, such as learning and working. According to a study by Chen (2016) on three developing-nation cities—Ahmedabad, India; Durban, South Africa; and Lima, Peru—urban workers in the informal sector primarily use low-end technology to support their jobs. Digital technology, including smartphones and the internet, is seen as cutting edge, and its usage varies widely in terms of intensity.

DIGITAL SOCIETY AND DIGITAL DIVIDE IN INDIAN CONTEXT

The remarkable speed with which information is shared across international networks is a defining feature of the digital society. The most notable aspect of digital society, where big data and data mining are essential, is the "super connected" life made possible by the "Internet of things" (Redshaw, 2020). Industry 4.0, or the fourth industrial revolution, brought about a global transition that is known as the digital society. Consumerism and the current sophisticated industrial age are strongly related, and this techno-social transition is in line with the latter's goals of increased market and industrial benefits. The political economy, society, and daily activities of all people are heavily regulated under late capitalism, or advanced capitalism, to the point that all human endeavours are digitalized and turn into commodities for commercial enterprises.

With the rapid growth of popular culture and social media in India, the consuming trend has brought up issues related to digital space, capitalization of digital space, digital activism, and the digital divide. Recently, social media has emerged as a digital phenomenon and a new reality. With the advent of Industry 4.0, a new digital society where everyone has unavoidable access to technology infrastructure and the Internet began. A digital, data-driven, networked industry known as “industry 4.0” is revolutionizing a number of industries, including labour, healthcare, human relations, marketing, and production (Banholzer,2022). People who are unable to access technology infrastructure and the Internet are isolated from both the global community and the mainstream society. When considering people’s access and capabilities, digital inequality and the digital gap emerge as significant issues.

Because social interactions, societal structure, social institutions, norms, values, culture, and social control are reinterpreted as intricate techno-social systems in the new digital world, the digital and physical societies are incompatible. The traditional activities of the physical society have been drastically changed by the technocratic social structure of the digital society. Technological, social, and economic advancements are all combined in the digital society. Since digital technologies have a profound impact on human existence and are widely integrated into it, it is impossible for any person to live in isolation from the digital society (Laskar, 2023).

DIGITALIZATION AND TREND OF POPULAR CULTURE CONSUMPTION

According to Oxfam International’s report from 2021, 77% of India’s wealth is held by the richest 10% of the population, demonstrating the country’s high inequality and widening class divide. Therefore, in a country like India, progress is not always validated by growth in consumption alone. In 2020, India had 468 million digital residents, a number that has continued to rise despite these obstacles because of the size of the nation. Reliance Jio started a revolution in India in 2007 by offering inexpensive, limitless 3G and 4G Internet connectivity. Jio, an Indian telecoms firm, was the first to offer free phone and data services when it debuted its commercial 4G services in 2016. Other telecom companies like Airtel and BSNL eventually adopted same strategy. Furthermore, the expansion of Jio, Airtel, BSNL, and other mobile phone providers was significantly aided by the partner policy of those firms, which started selling 4G handsets at significantly lower prices (Laskar, 2023). Due to the broad creation and consumption of popular culture, the culture business has profited from this rise. As a result, the Indian entertainment industry has been expanding quickly, despite socioeconomic difficulties and inequalities. The FICCI and EY (2020, 2021) study on Media and Entertainment in India states that in 2020, Indians used their phones for 4.5 hours a day, which is a considerable rise from 3.5 hours in 2019 and a 25% increase from 2017. India topped China, Mexico, Argentina, and South Korea in 2020 with the most time spent on phones globally, at 4.5 hours per day. Furthermore, Indian consumers logged on for 1,669 billion minutes in 2020—a 32% rise from 1,261 billion minutes in 2019.

THEORETICAL MODEL

The sociological discourse created by Manuel Castells, Pierre Bourdieu, and Max Weber serves as the basis for this work. By examining digital stratification in terms of sociocultural and economic factors, it seeks to explain why there are differences in affordability and accessibility

between the two groups of urban people. According to Weber (2018), research on the causes of inequality in modern society has to take status and power into account in addition to class-based affinities. This essay argues that the way that class, position, and power interact determines how digital life is organized. In doing so, it draws further explanations of the fundamental causes of the digital divide using the Weberian cultural perspective.

Weber's work will also be connected to the theoretical framework offered by another sociologist Pierre Bourdieu. Digital inequality is a topic that lends itself well to a Bourdieusian analysis, particularly his examination of capital forms. Bourdieu described capital as the accumulation of forms of labor, further subdivided into social, economic, and cultural categories. Specialized individual material assets are referred to as economic capital. Social assets that promote mobility in a stratified society, such education and fashion sense, can be considered forms of cultural capital. Membership in a group or a set of assets that form a network of relationships based on mutual recognition is implied by social capital. Scholars have notably extended this approach to the nascent area of digital divide studies by conceiving and operationalizing what is referred to as 'digital capital. According to Raggedda and Riui (2020), digital capital refers to the benefits that an individual or group receives from having access to and ownership of digital technologies, as well as digital skills and capabilities.

Following in the academic footsteps of Castells (2000), one may contend that the inclusion/exclusion binary structure, which is reflected in the digital inequality between the privileged and the disprivileged, is the fundamental building block of a network society. The exclusion is, nevertheless, of a qualitatively distinct kind. According to Castells, the underclass that belonged to peripheral regions was exploited in the early stages of industrial capitalism, but under the new network society framework, it is apparent that these groups are rendered completely irrelevant. Castells points out that the social networks that influence mainstream culture can be determined by the ongoing social, cultural, and educational restrictions on ICT access.

The theoretical frameworks presented by Weber, Bourdieu, and Castells persuasively argue that there is a critical connection between global crises like poverty, inequality, and exclusion and unequal access to knowledge.

METHODS

Doing the Interviews: at the Affluent and under Resourced City Areas

The study chose Kolkata, the capital city of West Bengal, India, as a place for investigation. The respondents included students, working youths, professionals, residents in affluent areas, and those living in low-resourced urban areas. Kolkata rose to prominence in 1756, particularly in England, when Siraj-ud-Dawlah, a Bengal ruler, conquered the fort. The British reclaimed the city in 1757, led by Robert Clive. The English initially constructed an elaborate transportation network via the Hugli-Ganges water system, but it was railroads, established in the 1850s, that effectively built linkages with the hinterland and the rest of India. By the end of the nineteenth century, the city had the highest concentration of trade firms in India and had developed a Western-style business area. The colonial city kept a clear distinction between the crowded and unplanned native quarters to the east and north of the Central Business District and the spacious and well-planned

quarters where Europeans lived in the south and south-east parts of the old city. After independence, the former European quarters were either converted into mansions for the Indian privileged or, as in the Park Street area, into commercial areas (Kolkata Municipal Corporation, see [Official Website of Kolkata Municipal Corporation \(kmcgov.in\)](http://Official Website of Kolkata Municipal Corporation (kmcgov.in))) Thus, it is not only the place of historical importance but also the earliest establishment of a commercial system in Kolkata, which becomes the cause of population density in the city.

The research article uses information gathered from semi-structured interviews that were done as a component of the current, wider study project. Interviews were conducted with total one hundred (100) students and other respondents from both affluent city and under-resourced urban areas. The method utilized to gather interviews was snow-ball sampling, which involved personal acquaintances. Because it enables the researcher to access people who might not be readily identified or accessible, it is beneficial for hard-to-reach or hidden populations. The interviews subsequently manually transcribed. This is an exploratory investigation; hence the inductive method was utilized to find categories, patterns, and themes. In this study, the case investigations of the respondents are set apart as “R” trailed by number identifiers.

OUTCOME AND INTERPRETATION OF THE STUDY

Background Information

The respondents (100) in this study reside in the Kolkata metropolitan city among the affluent societies (50) and under-resourced urban areas (50), and predominantly the affluent city areas. Most of the affluent city area residents are trilingual, who are comfortable in Bengali, Hindi, and English in communication, followed by the bilingual, who can speak in Bengali and Hindi only. The under-resourced urban areas residents are mostly monolingual, who can speak Bengali only, followed by bilingual, use Bengali and Hindi in communication, and then are trilingual. And their medium of education is mostly in English, followed by Hindi and Bengali.

Table 1 : Socio-demographic profile of the respondents from the affluent and under resourced city areas of Kolkata metropolitan city

Category	Frequency (N=100)			
Participants	Affluent city area (50)		Under-resourced urban areas (50)	
Gender	Male	25	Male	25
	Female	25	Female	25
Age group	15-25 years	10	15-25 years	16
	26-35 years	24	26-35 years	24
Language	Monolingual	00	Monolingual	28
	Bilingual	07	Bilingual	20
	Trilingual	42	Trilingual	02
	More than 3 languages	01	Multilingual (more than 3 languages)	00

Language	Monolingual	00	Monolingual	28
	Bilingual	07	Bilingual	20
	Trilingual	42	Trilingual	02
	More than 3 languages	01	Multilingual (more than 3 languages)	00
Medium of education	Bengali	05	Bengali	40
	Hindi	10	Hindi	10
	English	35	English	00
Family type	Joint family	14	Joint family	32
	Nuclear family	36	Nuclear family	18

Source : obtained from field survey and primary data

Identifying the Characteristics of Under-resourced Urban Areas

The widening digital divide in India is a result of the country's persistent socioeconomic division. It was discovered that the digital divide mostly existed in the economic and educational spheres in both rural and urban locations, as well as between affluent cities and under-resourced urban areas with inadequate resources. The main causes of the digital divide include inadequate socioeconomic conditions, restricted access to digital resources, and inadequate digital infrastructure in urban regions with low resources. Cities and wealthy neighbourhoods inside them, however, have access to digital amenities and are technologically savvy. There is a thorough explanation in the parts that follow.

In Indian cities, under-resourced regions are common and draw a sizable population that works in the unorganized sector. A few distinct traits that set under-resourced urban areas apart from rich urban areas were noted during the study conducted there. These attributes are revealed in Table 2.

Table 2 : Characteristics of under resourced urban areas

Under-resourced urban areas	<p>Better choice for less expensive, more affordable housing, however slums and suburban housing still exist.</p> <p>Lack of essential services and infrastructure.</p> <p>Persistently non-compliant land use pattern.</p> <p>Lack of a clear legal framework governing development, management, and planning.</p> <p>Comparatively cheaper cost of living than wealthy cities lack of levies, taxes, fees, tolls, etc.</p> <p>Lack of a rationalized traffic and transportation network, poor accessibility.</p> <p>High levels of land speculation as a result of declining land values</p> <p>Simple procedures for converting land.</p> <p>Deteriorated environment.</p>
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Source : Field survey & Author's own compilation

Identifying the Factors of Digital Divide

In Indian cities, social stratification and the digital gap are clearly visible. There is a big difference between people who live in affluent urban regions (the city dwellers) and people who live in under-resourced urban areas. In India, the number of people living in metropolitan regions with little resources has been rising. These locations offer insufficient amenities for digital life, restricted access to the internet, and a low standard of living. More than 100 million people—more than Australia’s total population—lived in metropolitan areas with inadequate resources as of 2022 (India Housing Report, 2022). Urban areas with few resources have been affected by digitalization, although not significantly because people there are already susceptible in many social and economic ways. Living in under-resourced metropolitan regions prevents people from accessing the digital economy, e-healthcare, digitalized education, or technology-based skills. They own cellphones, but the study found that their primary uses are for social media and popular culture. Even children who attend school are frequently observed lingering and engaging in numerous unethical and non-social behaviours on their phones. The stereotypical concepts about women also exist, which causes the ‘Gender Digital Divide.’ Individual, cognitive, family, and socio-cultural factors are present behind this (Tabassum & Nayek, 2021). Their counterparts who live in wealthy cities, on the other hand, have access to all modern amenities. In light of sociocultural and economic elements, the study’s analysis attempts to comprehend and assess the digital divide in both types of affluent city and under-resourced urban locations. The factors noted during the field survey are shown in the table 3 below.

Table 3 : Factors of Digital divide

Factors of Digital divide	Components of the factors
Socio-cultural factors	Basic functional literacy, linguistic problem, stereotypical concepts on women, difference between the actual use and meaningful use
Socio-economic factors	Infrastructure and availability, accessibility and affordability

Source : Field Survey & Author’s Own Compilation

According to Al-Jumeily et al. (2014), the socio-cultural elements are language, credentials/skills, and enabling circumstances. According to Srite & Karahanna (2006), an extended model of technology acceptance as moderators incorporates cultural values such as individualism/collectivism, power distance, uncertainty avoidance, and masculinity/femininity.

Socio-cultural Factors

Basic Functional Literacy and Social Ownership

The digital divide includes both digital literacy and skills in addition to access to technology. The most important barrier to ICT nowadays is basic functional literacy. This type of literacy cannot be limited to paper forms in the context of mass media development; it must also take into account new digital media, the screen being the first, and the fact that read/write skills nowadays must be designed with multimedia integration in mind (as sounds and images incorporated

into text tend to be both an integral part and an integrated part of communication). Without sufficient guidance and assistance, people might not have the self-assurance or understanding to use digital tools, execute online research, or traverse digital platforms. The similar narrative shared by a male respondent, R (36), a twenty three years-old student, with college graduate degree, from under-resourced urban area, and part time employee of a shopping mall believes,

“Computers and the internet should be taught to people in classes. Then, they will learn about the internet, be able to use it, and comprehend its benefits.”

R (32) belongs to the under-resourced urban area, a student of twenty year student, and comes from an extended family gives his practical view regarding ICT use, which is different from the last one’s opinion.

“I am a student. Learning how to use the internet doesn’t require any particular abilities. It’s easy to spot someone using the internet if you see them once. There are no academic requirements for using the internet. I gained knowledge of the internet via practice.”

The above case studies are showing the ‘Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)’, because the respondents use ICT and gained knowledge via practice, and seeking for the prior training too.

The condition of women about the digital literacy has shared by R (25), who is a twenty years student from an extended family and from under-resourced urban area. She shared her friend’s situation regarding ICT literacy, that,

“I completed my higher secondary education. I am currently trying to take admission in college. I’m not good at using the internet since I don’t know how to utilize it. I did not receive a sufficient knowledge of computers in school. My friend took computer theory classes in school, but she never received any hands-on instruction.”

In these women centric cases, the theory of ‘Cultural lag’, where the gap between materialistic and non-materialistic culture is identified due to not receiving sufficient knowledge and got theory classes only on computer. The ‘Developmental Intergroup Theory’, which is about individual’s family upbringing concerning ICT use and digital divide can be related to their situation that influences the processes by which children identify groups as targets of stereotyping and prejudice, as well as how children acquire and create the traits (i.e., stereotypes) and affective responses (i.e., prejudices) associated with these groups within their culture (Bigler & Liben, 2006).

The computer and internet training at early age and practice are the suitable recommendation to minimize the digital gap on basic functional literacy and ownership of the digital tools. The scenario is different when it comes to the affluent city areas. From the survey and interviews, no such complaints were found from the affluent areas’ respondents on functional literacy and social ownership; moreover, they strongly agree with the fact of coping with the digital boom for the better future.

Linguistic problem

Considering the pervasiveness of language in our lives, it is also an essential component of ICTs. A linguistic system is nearly always necessary when using ICTs. On this point, there is an issue since the languages spoken by the people who are receiving these ICTs and the languages that are configured in the electronic devices or sources diverge. Following the emergence of American supremacy in global politics and technology, English became the de facto language virtually everywhere. When it comes to computers and the internet, English is the most widely used language. These days, the most basic measure of the digital divide is internet access, thus language becomes increasingly significant in this regard. Non-English speakers find themselves with restricted opportunities in the digital world. They must acquire the language in order to access the countless advantages offered by the internet. The issue is made worse by considering that English is used in the design and development of the majority of computer hardware and software. New computer-related products and applications undergo a difficult translation procedure before they are prepared for usage by non-English speaking populations (Yaman, 2015).

A user's attitude toward technology is significantly influenced by the language used in technology. Technology may be used easily and flexibly when its language is clear and easy to grasp, which fosters favourable attitudes toward the technology. Conversely, negative attitudes toward technology are produced by technical terminology that is complex and difficult to understand. Not being efficient in English language is another barrier in order to operate the devices for the under-resourced urban areas' users. R (41), a thirty-two-year-old, male student residing in under-resourced urban area from Bengali medium schools, gave his views on coping strategy with linguistic problems that,

“I am not efficient in English language and studied till 10+2 from local Govt. school and presently I am self-employed and pursuing bachelor degree from open university. It's difficult to access several options of my smartphone. Some technical features also make me confuse and I use the limited facilities of my smartphone, such as receiving and making calls, playing youtube, whatsapp and UPI for the money transaction which I learnt from my friends. There is no need of Desktop/Laptop to use in my home and for my work purpose.”

R (75), a male student who belongs to a Hindi-speaking family, took education from a Hindi-medium school with higher secondary qualification and from an under-resourced urban area, and gave a solution to deal with a linguistic-related digital gap or problem, i.e.,

“I'm pursuing bachelor degree from an open university and doing job as a daily wages employee in a shop. I convert the English language in Hindi by the help of certain application and features of my cell phone. I still face some technical issues in advance level during using my cellphone. I don't need Desktop/Laptop, because it's not useful to me.”

An affluent city area woman, R (51) who is twenty-three years old, a graduate, and with IT degree, medium of education being English, shows her different story regarding ICT's

significance and language barrier to it than the previous case studies, which are from under-resourced area respondents. She believes,

“I am an IT trainee. I don’t feel any language or any kind of barriers when using digital devices. Use of smartphone, laptop and internet connection is daily part of my communication and work.”

R (63), a college student from an affluent city area resident reveals his zero complaint about his ICT ownership, internet facility and purpose of use with no language barrier to utilize it. He believes,

“I am a college student. Smartphone, Laptop, internet connection is very useful for my academic purpose, communication and entertainment. I don’t think English or technical languages and other features are my barriers of using it.”

The few above case studies are revealing how linguistic gap creates digital gap and leads to the cultural lag, where materialistic and non-materialistic culture don’t go symmetrically. It also shows a number of cope up strategies to mitigate the linguistic gap by the respondents by transferred the language setting into their local language. The case studies analysis shows the dichotomy between affluent city areas and under-resourced urban areas regarding linguistic related digital gap which is primarily related to the efficiency in English language or not.

Stereotypical Concept about Women

Women in India are not only more likely to be unpaid or underpaid workers, but most of them also have to shoulder the burden of caregiving in a traditional Indian household owing to gender roles and institutional structures. This leaves them with limited time dedicated to learning new technical skills. Further, scientific and technological education and overall education are generally not prioritized for women and girls. Thus, the likelihood of them being able to use the Internet goes down significantly (Antonio & Tuffley, 2014). The analyses of NSS 75th Round data on digital affordability and accessibility thus clearly suggest higher affordability for women compared to men due to improved household economic conditions. However, accessibility to digital resources for women remains poor when compared to men due to specific socio-cultural barriers (Dubey et al. 2024).

Corneliussen (2003) has acknowledged three leading discourses that link gender and I.C.T. discourses in his study in Norway. (i) A gender-blind discourse in which the female gender is not regarded as a concern in technology usage in the same way that males are.

(ii) A masculine discourse, in which the connection between men and technology was regarded as intense, and (iii) A feminine discourse denotes the ability to recognise femininity discourse while ignoring the strong association between men, masculinity, and technology.

The below case studies reveal the digital disparity between the male and female respondents of affluent city and under-privileged city areas, which leads to the digital gap and the theory of cultural gap.

The ‘Social Role Theory’, gender division of work that is typical of a society, is the source of commonly held gender stereotypes (Eagly, 1987), and the ‘Gender Blind Discourse’ approach is shown from the answer of R (72), who is twenty-one years old female student from an under-resourced area’s extended family’s housewife, says,

“Boys use the internet more frequently than females do. Girls have to take care of the house, go to college, and then study since they don’t have enough free time. Usually, boys go to the café or another location to access the internet. Boys gather in groups, share messages, listen to music, etc. We stay inside the house. We attend college and immediately return home.”

R (84) is a college girl from an extended family of under-resourced urban areas represents her condition and boundaries regarding access to digital device and the thought of the society about proving ownership of digital tools to their girl children. Her situation is similar to the “Developmental Intergroup Theory” which addresses how a person’s familial upbringing affects how they use ICT and how the digital gap may be connected to their circumstances. These factors can have an impact on the way youngsters identify groups as the objects of stereotypes and prejudice. She says,

“As a college student, I don’t have much free time. Whenever I have free time, I visit the cybercafé. It may seem tiring to utilize the internet on a daily basis. Girls do not have authorization to use the internet on their mobile phones, but boys do. Girls don’t even have smart phones, so they can’t ask for permission to access the internet.”

R (31), a nineteen year old college girl from the under-resourced urban areas respondent says,

“As a student, I do not have access to the internet on my phone. The family forbids me from leaving the house, and the computer cafés are too far away.”

The support of men is shown towards their female counterparts about utilization of digital tools explicitly by denying the ‘Gender-Blind Discourse’ in which the female gender is not viewed as relevant in technology usage in the same manner that males are, and ‘Masculine Discourse’, in which the relationship between men and technology has been described as fierce. R (45), who is a male of thirty-six years with a postgraduate degree, administrator by profession, and from an affluent city area, gives his optimistic and liberal opinion about mitigating the gender-based digital gap. The same view was shared by the male respondents R (3), R (7), and R (25), which is,

“Technology should be used regardless of time, geographical location, gender, race, and ethnicity for the betterment of society and proceed to the information age. Every member of my family gets an equal opportunity to use digital devices and the internet.”

Researchers have extended the concept of digital capital by elaborating on appropriations of Bourdieu’s formulation of capitals. This finding can also be utilized to investigate the gendered nature of differing quantities of digital capital. Because girls and women are assigned a secondary role in society, feminist researchers have observed that gender has a significant link to the development of social capital position relative to males, therefore they have less access to

resources for health, education, and literacy (Burt, 1998). Using this reasoning further, it can be said that gaining digital capital via the accessibility and Online resource accessibility is significantly impacted by the gendered control mechanisms outlined above.

Actual use and meaningful use

Possessing the ability to work with digital tools and comprehend conceptual and cultural concerns related to the digital world are prerequisites for making effective and efficient use of ICT. It is feasible to address some of the needs in the field of development by using ICT, which is not limited to gaming or interpersonal communication.

The below case studies are instances of the 'Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)', where users' views and level of convenience with digital technologies influence their behavioural purpose of using them (Das & Bhattacharyya, 2023). The case studies are showing that the respondents use technology for their work, communication, and entertainment purposes mainly.

R (2), from an affluent city area, a thirty-four-year male with an IT profession, gives his view about the use of ICT and digital technology. He says,

"I use the internet to check official emails, forward client complaints to my seniors via e-mail, pay for my phone and internet recharge, and also for the family members' mobile phones, make money transfers, and online shopping. The majority of people here only use the internet for entertainment and communication, Facebook, and WhatsApp."

R (54), a male student of a postgraduate course and from an affluent city area, says, "Being a postgraduate student, I use technology for academic purposes with communication and entertainment. I acquire various knowledge from YouTube tutorials that enhance my knowledge."

R (81), a twenty-five-year-old female and medical student, says,

"I believe that digital devices and the internet make our lives easier by introducing net banking facilities, online payment, online booking on railways, and flights, which is commendable. And for the academic purpose, it brings revolution by giving easy information access."

The third level of the digital divide, articulated by van Deursen and Helsper (2015), focuses on the outcomes or benefits of digital use, as demonstrated by case studies and respondents' histories of ICT usage, which reveal a positive trend in both affluent and under-resourced urban locations.

Socio-economic Factors

Infrastructure and Availability

According to Warren (2007), a discrete sector of the population suffers significant and possibly indefinite lags in its adoption of ICT due to circumstances beyond its immediate control constitutes digital exclusion. Territorial digital exclusion is one kind of this, which is a reflection of differences in the quality and availability of telecommunications infrastructure at various spatial scales.

It is evident that access to the ICT cannot be granted in the absence of a suitable infrastructure. It is important to understand “access” not only in terms of geographic reach (e.g., granting access in remote areas) but also in terms of economic reach (enabling access for those with limited financial resources). Cost restrictions frequently prevent low-income urban areas from using ICT services. In some places, there may be less competition among internet service providers, which can raise prices and make it difficult for consumers to afford monthly internet services. The main cause of this is digital redlining, when internet service providers purposefully invested less in minority and low-income areas in the belief that they will make more money in affluent, privilege neighbourhoods. An assessment of internet access points is crucial to understanding the infrastructural barriers faced by users.

R (44), twenty two years old male student from an Under-resourced urban area stated about the fact related to the internet network problem and digital gap. Others few respondents are from the under-resourced areas complaint about the same problem. R (44) says,

“The network at home is either non-existent or inadequate. I leave the house and head outside to use the internet or head toward the road. There are more network issues when you go deeper within the locality, but the network is better outside in the open air.”

The scene has changed when it turns to the affluent city areas. The respondents from the affluent areas have good infrastructure and think about privacy too while using the web. Some of these tech-efficient people also address some digital availability and infrastructural issues, which are not negligible.

R (53), a twenty seven year old female respondent from affluent city areas with IT profession says,

“In my opinion, mobile internet provides access to information at the appropriate time. If not, it would be necessary to attend the cyber café and complete all tasks before departing. Hence, using mobile internet to stay connected is preferable. But in our flat broadband service is not as expected.”

R (91), a twenty four year female Post-graduate student states that,

“I like to utilize a touchscreen mobile device to access the internet. Using it is simpler than using a laptop or a PC. Cyber cafés are prohibited for use in private. Thus, the smartphone is your best alternative.”

Accessibility and Affordability

In cities, mainly in under-resourced urban areas the expense of digital gadgets can also be a major obstacle to digital inclusion. Many people in low-income neighbourhoods find it difficult to afford digital devices like tablets, laptops, and PCs, and a high speed internet facility as well. There are also issues on regular internet recharge and price hike which lead to the digital divide in spite of having demand. The below case studies are showing different situations of the respondents from both of the city areas; under-resourced and affluent areas, where the socio-economic conditions are different for all and which caused digital divide and exclusion.

R (25), a twenty four year old male with graduate degree and now searching for suitable job and from an under-resourced urban area says,

“Most people are unable to pay the monthly internet packages. Because of this, not many members of the community own it. Although some residents of our areas have access to regular internet packs, I have not.”

R (50), a twenty year male respondent with a private job and from an under-resourced urban area stated about the network issue in their areas. He says,

“What’s the need of spending money on internet packs if you don’t get any speed or range? It’s not affordable if you pay money and receive inferior service. In order to get some connectivity, we have to sit outside.”

R (37), a twenty-five-year-old male respondent from an under-resourced urban area, complained about the poor service of a cyber café that is nearby their area. He says,

“Because there weren’t enough computers and they were sometimes packed, we had to wait our turn at the cyber cafés. The outdated PCs would cause the speed to be slow. This was how I would sometimes waste thirty minutes.”

The affluent city dwellers’ conditions are different than their under-resourced areas counterparts. R (48), a twenty-three-year-old female graduate, says,

“Although there is a cyber café, internet privacy is non-existent. Thus, the smartphone is your best alternative.”

R (13), a thirty-year-old male and doctor by profession, talks about the obsolete equipment issue, and he says,

“The obsolete equipment’s issues make me feel annoying. The technological advancement is increasing frequently.”

Bourdieu doubted the importance of economic factors. The social and economic capital in this case is further converted into digital capital, so solidifying the dominance of the wealthy elite at the top of the social strata, where they are typically concentrated. While the under privileged section of peripheral regions was clearly rendered entirely irrelevant under the new framework of network society, Castells (2000) claims that in the initial phases of industrial capitalism, this under privileged section was exploited. It might be argued that the core component of a network society is the inclusion/exclusion binary framework, which is mirrored in the digital inequalities between the privileged and the disprivileged.

Conclusion and recommendation

The study finds several obstructions to the digital divide, including the educational system, language barriers, low literacy rates, gender stereotype issues, economic barriers, and infrastructural issues identified from the analysis of this study. That is to say, there are multiple digital divides rather than just one, and in order to close them, numerous and varied initiatives are required. The difference in possibilities to access ICT and use the internet for a wide range

of purposes across individuals, households, businesses, and geographic areas at different socioeconomic levels is known as the “digital divide.” Based on comparative research between affluent metropolitan areas and under-resourced urban areas, it is necessary to minimize the digital divide in these areas’ livelihoods through innovative solutions.

The results can be sorted into two categories. Regarding digital affordability, even though economic class was not explored in depth as a variable, it was recurrently used to explain the purchasing limits of marginalized groups who live in under-resourced urban areas.

Models for researchers, social scientists, and librarian technologists must be created in order to ensure that technological innovation and policymaking satisfy local requirements. Improved connectivity is required in under-resourced urban areas. Internet service providers and telecom firms should prioritize these areas by offering higher-quality internet services and introducing affordable internet packages that are affordable for the majority of residents.

It implies the need to reduce entry-level pricing and reconcile them with income disparities. In sociological terms, efforts must be made to increase the perceived value of technology while also incorporating digital resources into the spending priorities of underprivileged groups. We should concentrate on the low-Internet user population, which includes women, the elderly, and children in all locations, in order to close the digital divide. Inequalities exist due to socio-cultural factors. Despite women’s increased affordability, gender stereotypes and unpaid care work limit their access to internet knowledge and digital abilities. Initiatives to raise gender awareness and challenge prejudices are critical for promoting 'digital inclusion'.

Both the mobile applications and the contents should be created in the local languages. Since the majority of students from under-resourced areas attend public schools where there is no emphasis on the English language. Additionally, the indigenous languages which are widely spoken and understood by the people living in these places. Therefore, it is possible to propose the idea to close the digital gap.

A moral and ethical framework, volunteer support, non-governmental organizations, and community services can all help to advance the agendas of awareness on ICT use, training programs, and relevance in our daily lives so that people in the majority of underprivileged areas learn about them, participate in reducing the digital divide for welfare, and demand that the government and private sector find a solution. In an effort to eventually encourage digital equity and inclusion, this study argues for a reciprocal relationship between affordability and accessibility, highlighting the need for coordinated attempts to support digital affordability and skill development for vulnerable groups residing in under-resourced urban areas mainly.

Addressing the digital divide in India is an intricate problem that necessitates a multifaceted solution. The study attempted to present an appraisal of the existing scenario based on exploratory research and the authors’ own self-investigation in a comparative way between affluent and under-resourced areas in Kolkata, India. It is possible to design a study to collect primary data that will deliver a larger, more diverse sample and, in a comparable manner, on the consumption and expenditure on digital services, allowing for more robust analyses to be performed by covering other metropolitan regions in India and other countries. By offering different solutions to more people from different diasporas, future research could try to get beyond all of those

obstacles and further our understanding of how to improve the digital facilities and abilities of tech-challenged, under-resourced urban regions mainly.

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